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Security tools in a continuous integration/continuous deployment pipeline

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Abstract: Integrating a vulnerability database into a Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline is essential for enhancing the security posture of software development processes. This integration allows for automated identification and remediation of known vulnerabilities in applications and their dependencies. The process involves selecting a suitable vulnerability database, configuring API access, and embedding API calls within the CI/CD workflow to check for vulnerabilities at various stages of development. Additionally, it encompasses the analysis of vulnerability data, automated dependency management, and the generation of security reports. Continuous monitoring for newly reported vulnerabilities ensures ongoing security, while training and documentation foster a culture of security awareness within development teams.

Keywords: CI/CD Pipeline, Vulnerability Database, API Integration, Security Automation, GitHub Security Advisories.

Introduction. Software Configuration Management (SCM) is a crucial phase in software development that enhances the management, organization, and control of changes to various elements, including requirements, code, and teams throughout the software development lifecycle. Continuous improvement is essential, as enhancements and changes in functionality are often integrated into the final product.

Before introducing changes to the system, a thorough analysis must be conducted. These changes should be documented prior to implementation, communicated in detail both before and after, and managed in a manner that enhances quality and minimizes errors to mitigate risks to the entire system. This underscores the necessity of system configuration management, which addresses these complexities and facilitates appropriate software adjustments [1].

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Effective change control is vital; without proper oversight, changes can disrupt organized programming efforts. Thus, SCM plays an integral role in engineering project management. Its primary objective is to boost productivity while minimizing errors. SCM also facilitates accountability within teams by tracking who made specific changes, enhancing collaboration [2].

Methods. Integrating security tools into a Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline involves several steps to ensure that security checks are automated and embedded within the development lifecycle. Here's a step-by-step guide:

1. «Choose Your Tools»

- Select the appropriate security tools based on your needs (e.g., SAST, DAST, IaC scanning). Ensure they are compatible with your CI/CD platform (e.g., Jenkins, GitLab CI, CircleCI).

2. «Define the Pipeline Structure»

- Outline the stages of your CI/CD pipeline where security checks will occur. Common stages include:

- Code Commit: Run SAST tools after code is committed.

- Build: Conduct IaC scanning during the build phase.

- Testing: Execute DAST tools to assess the security of applications in a staging environment.

- Deployment: Perform final checks before deploying to production.

3. «Configure Security Tools»

- Set up the security tools with the necessary configurations, such as:

- Scanning Rules: Customize rules based on your security policies.

- Authentication: Ensure tools can access the necessary resources (e.g., repositories, cloud environments).

- Thresholds: Define thresholds for passing or failing builds based on security findings.

4. «Integrate Tools into the CI/CD Pipeline»

- For Jenkins:

- Use plugins for SAST (e.g., SonarQube Scanner) and DAST (e.g., OWASP ZAP).

- Add steps in your Jenkinsfile to run security scans at the appropriate stages.

```
``groovy
pipeline {
  agent any
  stages {
    stage('Build') {
      steps {
```

```
        sh 'mvn clean package' // Example build command
    }
}
stage('SAST') {
    steps {
        script {
            // Run SAST tool
            sh 'sonar-scanner'
        }
    }
}
stage('DAST') {
    steps {
        script {
            // Run DAST tool
            sh 'zap.sh -cmd -quickurl http://yourapp.com'
        }
    }
}
// Additional stages...
}
}
...

```

- For GitLab CI:

- Use built-in security scanning features or define jobs in ``.gitlab-ci.yml``.

```
``yaml
```

```
stages:
```

- build
- test
- security

```
build:
```

```
  stage: build
```

```
  script:
```

- mvn clean package

```
sast:
```

```
  stage: security
```

```
  script:
```

- sonar-scanner

```
dast:
```

```
  stage: security
```

```
  script:
```

```
- zap-cli quick-scan --url http://yourapp.com
...
- For CircleCI:
- Integrate tools using CircleCI configuration in `.circleci/config.yml`.
```yaml
version: 2.1
jobs:
 build:
 docker:
 - image: circleci/openjdk:8
 steps:
 - checkout
 - run:
 name: Build Project
 command: mvn clean package
 - run:
 name: Run SAST
 command: sonar-scanner
 - run:
 name: Run DAST
 command: zap.sh -cmd -quickurl http://yourapp.com
...

```

#### 5. «Set Up Notifications and Reporting»

- Configure notifications for build failures due to security issues (e.g., via email, Slack).
- Generate reports from the tools and publish them as part of the build artifacts for review.

#### 6. «Continuous Monitoring and Updates»

- Regularly update your security tools to ensure they are using the latest signatures and rules.
- Review and refine the security configurations, thresholds, and integration processes based on feedback and evolving security landscapes.

#### 7. «Training and Awareness»

- Ensure team members understand the security tools and their integration, fostering a culture of security within the development process.

Results. Integrating a vulnerability database into your CI/CD pipeline enhances your ability to identify and remediate known vulnerabilities in your application and its dependencies. Here's how to effectively integrate a vulnerability database:

#### 1. «Choose a Vulnerability Database»

- Select a vulnerability database that fits your needs. Popular options include:

- «National Vulnerability Database (NVD)»
- «CVE Details»
- «Snyk»
- «WhiteSource»
- «GitHub Security Advisories»

## 2. «API Access and Configuration»

- Most vulnerability databases provide APIs for querying vulnerabilities. Obtain API keys or access tokens as required.

- Familiarize yourself with the API documentation to understand how to fetch vulnerability data.

## 3. «Integrate API Calls in the CI/CD Pipeline»

- Add steps in your CI/CD pipeline to query the vulnerability database for known vulnerabilities based on your project's dependencies.

# Example Integration Steps:

For Jenkins:

```
``groovy
pipeline {
 agent any
 stages {
 stage('Build') {
 steps {
 sh 'mvn clean package'
 }
 }
 stage('Check Vulnerabilities') {
 steps {
 script {
 // Example command to check for vulnerabilities
 sh 'curl -H "Authorization: Bearer YOUR_API_KEY"
"https://api.vuln.db.com/v1/projects/YOUR_PROJECT_ID/vulnerabilities"'
 }
 }
 }
 }
}
```

For GitLab CI:

```
``yaml
stages:
```

- build
- check\_vulnerabilities

build:

stage: build

script:

- mvn clean package

check\_vulnerabilities:

stage: check\_vulnerabilities

script:

- curl -H "Authorization: Bearer YOUR\_API\_KEY"

"https://api.vuln.db.com/v1/projects/YOUR\_PROJECT\_ID/vulnerabilities"

```

For CircleCI:

```yaml

version: 2.1

jobs:

build:

docker:

- image: circleci/openjdk:8

steps:

- checkout

- run:

name: Build Project

command: mvn clean package

- run:

name: Check for Vulnerabilities

command: curl -H "Authorization: Bearer YOUR\_API\_KEY"

"https://api.vuln.db.com/v1/projects/YOUR\_PROJECT\_ID/vulnerabilities"

```

4. «Analyze and Act on the Data»

- Parse the response from the vulnerability database to check for any vulnerabilities relevant to your project's dependencies.

- Set thresholds for failures based on the severity of reported vulnerabilities (e.g., fail the build if critical vulnerabilities are found).

5. «Automate Dependency Management»

- Use dependency management tools that can automatically check for updates and patches based on vulnerability reports:

- Snyk: Integrates with CI/CD pipelines and checks for vulnerabilities in dependencies.

- Dependabot: Automatically creates pull requests to update dependencies with known vulnerabilities.

6. «Generate Reports»

- Configure your pipeline to generate reports summarizing vulnerabilities found, their severity, and recommended actions.

- Store these reports as artifacts for future reference and audits.

7. «Continuous Monitoring»

- Implement ongoing monitoring of dependencies and vulnerability databases. This can include scheduled jobs in your CI/CD pipeline to regularly check for newly reported vulnerabilities.

8. «Training and Documentation»

- Educate your team on how to interpret vulnerability reports and the processes for remediating vulnerabilities.

- Document procedures for handling identified vulnerabilities within the team.

Discussion. Configuration management is vital for managing complex software systems. The absence of effective SCM can lead to significant issues regarding system reliability, uptime, and scalability. Many modern software development tools incorporate SCM functions, highlighting its importance in the development process [3-8].

Integrating security tools into a CI/CD pipeline is essential for maintaining a secure development process. By automating security checks at various stages, teams can identify and address vulnerabilities early, reducing the risk of security incidents in production environments [9-13].

Conclusion. Integrating a vulnerability database into your CI/CD pipeline is essential for maintaining secure software development practices. By automatically checking for known vulnerabilities, your team can proactively address potential security issues, ensuring a more robust and secure application.

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